

INFLUENCE OF SPECIMEN GEOMETRY AND UD PLY LAYUP ON THERMOPLASTIC WELDED DOUBLE-NOTCHED TENSION TEST SPECIMEN BY USE OF MECHANICAL AND VIRTUAL TESTING

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ABSTRACT

Thermoplastic composites can play a key role in developing future forms of transportation due to their high mechanical performance as well as their wide range of automatable joining and manufacturing methods. Thermoplastic welding techniques like induction and resistance welding provide flexible joining methods for many applications such as skin-stringer joints in an aircraft fuselage. With various welding processes existing, finding a suitable testing method to compare these processes would be beneficial. This paper shows the sensitivity of an ASTM D3165 based testing method (designated as double-notched tension test in this paper) especially to notch depth, as well as the three different laminate layups. It highlights the challenges to sample preparation and result interpretation, as well as the suitability of the testing method for the comparison of different welding techniques. Virtual testing is performed with a continuum damage finite element model, which is capable of mapping inter and intra-laminar failure, as well as failure of the welding zone itself to gain insight into the mechanical behavior of the tested sample.

1 INTRODUCTION

Upcoming urban and advanced air mobility (UAM & AAM), as well as new generation single aisle aircraft raise the need to evolve established materials and processes to enable manufacturers to satisfy the rising demand for all types of aircraft. Global commercial aircraft OEM forecast that traffic will more than double in the next two decades, requiring more than 40,000 aircraft deliveries, depending on high-rate capable production technologies. The Multi-Functional Fuselage Demonstrator (MFFD) developed and manufactured as part of the Clean Sky 2 Program with 14 project participants shows the application of over 40 airframe production technologies, highlighting dustless joining with thermoplastic welding methods. [1]

Manufacturing targets of electric vertical take-off and landing vehicle (eVTOL) OEM have been constantly adapted over the last years [2] and are highly depending on regulatory requirements, which are widely still work in progress like in the “Innovate28” plan of the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA). Nevertheless, when successfully regulated, that type of aircraft is capable of further improving urban transportation [3], since it offers a safer, quieter, more economic aircraft, compared to common vertical take-off and landing vehicles such as helicopters. [4]

Essential for the application of this material class is the understanding and consideration of various factors, like material behavior and testing, process-specific characteristics or numerical simulation methods. This paper addresses the applicability of a specific testing method (ASTM D3165) for thermoplastic welded joints as well as its numerical analysis with finite element (FE) simulation to find out if it's suitable for the quantitative comparison of different adherend architectures and welding procedures.

2 TEST DESCRIPTION

The test selected to compare different welding techniques is based on the ASTM D3165 - "Standard Test Method for Strength Properties of Adhesives in Shear by Tension Loading of Single-Lap-Joint Laminated Assemblies" [5] and further designated as double-notched tension test (DNT) within this paper. The schematical test setup can be seen in Figure 1. There are several sound reasons for choosing that specific testing method. Firstly, the geometrically induced secondary bending is reduced, compared to the commonly used single lap shear test, since the specimen is providing a higher bending stiffness outside the shear zone due to increased specimen thickness. Also edge effects showing up in joining and manufacturing processes, for instance during induction welding, can be reduced. Examples would include no excess matrix material which would normally squeeze out at the overlap edges of a single lap shear test (Kupski et. al [6] considered the induced skew for adhesively bonded single lap joints) or increased current densities near the edge [7,8] when joining with induction welding. Further, the steps of the test procedure show low complexity, which enables an efficient execution of test campaigns on common universal testing machines.

Figure 1: Schematical test setup and layup description.

The load is applied with a displacement rate of 1.27 mm/min via clamps to the specimen, where the load is transferred to the shear zone through a combination of shear and peel forces, resulting in a multiaxial stress state of the specimen. This scenario reflects critical, as well as relevant loading conditions when thinking of welded, thin-walled composite shell components.

3 SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION

The material used in this research is Toray® Cetex® TC1225, a unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced semi-crystalline low melt polyaryletherketone (PAEK) Tape from Toray Advanced Composites (TAC), the Netherlands. Considering future component manufacturing, the UD tape material is processed to laminate plates in a hot press, previous the actual joining procedure. This way, the material is experiencing the pressure and temperature it would receive in an actual manufacturing process like thermoforming. That's reasonable since the high process temperatures around 400°C can lead to degradation of the thermoplastic matrix material, which stayed well below 5% within this research.

After the hot press consolidation, the manufactured composite laminate plates are co-consolidated in an autoclave according to the processing guidelines for TC1225 LMPAEEK composites from TAC, providing sample plates, from which the actual specimen are manufactured by milling. The specimens tested have a total length of 175 mm, a sample width of 25 mm and a notch distance of 12.7 mm. The notch depth as well as the thickness of the laminate varied over the specimen.

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

This study employs the finite element analysis software *Abaqus/Explicit* to perform dynamic structural simulations of the Double-Notched Tension (DNT) test. The numerical model is designed to replicate the experimental setup with high fidelity, enabling detailed investigation of damage initiation and progression within the composite structure. The following sections describe the modeling approach, material definitions, boundary conditions, and contact formulations used in the simulation framework.

4.1 Material Parameter

Due to the limited availability of material-specific parameters, the simulation model was based on data from the literature corresponding to a similar material system—an unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced high-performance thermoplastic polymer. The material parameters used in the simulations are summarized in Table 1.

Material parameter		Value
E_1	[MPa]	138300
$E_{2,3}$	[MPa]	10400
$\nu_{12,13}$	–	0.316
ν_{23}	–	0.487
$G_{12,13}$	[MPa]	5190
G_{23}	[MPa]	3500*
X_T	[MPa]	2350
X_C	[MPa]	1621
Y_T	[MPa]	87
Y_C	[MPa]	273
$S_{12,5\%}$	[MPa]	90
S_{13}	[MPa]	90
S_{23}	[MPa]	90
G_{Ic}	[kJ/m ²]	0.7
G_{IIc}	[kJ/m ²]	1.45
η_{BK}	–	2.9
ζ_{1+}	[kJ/m ²]	125
ζ_{1-}	[kJ/m ²]	61
ζ_{2+}	[kJ/m ²]	1.12
ζ_{2-}	[kJ/m ²]	18.3

* $G_{23} = E_3 / (2 * (1 + \nu_{23}))$

Table 1: Material parameter for numerical simulation. [9, 10, 11]

4.2 Modelling Technique

An explicit finite element model was developed employing continuum shell elements to represent the composite plies. Interply and welding zone behavior were incorporated using a general cohesive contact formulation. Each individual ply was discretized with a single element through its thickness, and the built-in Hashin continuum damage model in Abaqus was utilized to simulate energy-based matrix and fiber damage, as well as ply failure.

The interply and welding zones were modeled using general contact with defined contact pairs, each assigned cohesive properties to capture energy-based cohesive damage and failure mechanisms. Load application was implemented by coupling the specimen's end surfaces to a reference point via tie constraints, where boundary conditions were imposed. A steadily increasing velocity was applied at the reference point to introduce the quasistatic displacement speed of the testing machine. Figure 2 shows a schematical representation of the FE Model.

A mesh convergence study was performed to validate the accuracy of the explicit dynamic structural simulations conducted in Abaqus/Explicit. The model was discretized using the SC8R elements. Several mesh densities were evaluated, focusing on key response parameters such as stress distribution and nodal displacements. Convergence was observed with a mesh consisting of approximately 438,000 elements and 897,000 nodes, beyond which further refinement produced negligible changes in the results. This mesh configuration was therefore adopted for all subsequent analyses to ensure computational efficiency without compromising accuracy.

To find out how valid the resulting simulation outcomes of this modelling technique are, the test shown in [11] was simulated with the modelling technique and simulation data described and shown above. The resulting failure load of the simulation is well within the test range shown in [11].

Figure 2: Schematical representation of FE model.

4.3 Virtual Testing of Notch Depth Variation

To investigate the impact of different parameters, a virtual testing is performed. Specifically, a variation of the notch depth for three different Layups is presented within this paper.

During the research it was found that the notches, which are milled in the double-notched tension specimens, are one of the most challenging topics in the manufacturing process of the test samples. For that reason, the effect of possible deviations in the depth of the notches was investigated by virtual testing. In more detail, the notch depth varied from ± 2 plies around the welding plane, which would result in a total amount of possible configurations of $2^5 = 32$ for two notches. That number was reduced to 15 when accounting for symmetries. The simulated configurations can be seen in Figure 2, where the notch-overlap u is introduced in Equation 1 as the difference between the total of the notch depths d_1 and d_2 and the laminate thickness T , where all values are discrete with increments of the ply thickness t . A positive notch-overlap indicates the number of milled-through plies, whereas a negative notch-overlap shows the number of continuous plies, which do not get machined at all.

$$u = (d_1 + d_2) - T \quad (1)$$

$$d_1, d_2, T \in \{n \cdot t \mid n \in \mathbb{N}^0\}$$

Figure 2: Virtual tested notch depth configurations.

5 RESULTS

The results of the virtual testing of the notch depth variation can be seen in Figure 3. For comparison, the resulting failure loads of the respective simulations have been normalized about configuration 0 of layup 0. The graph shows that some laminate configurations are more sensitive to the introduced notch overlap than others. For laminate 1 the notch overlap has a high impact on the resulting failure load, where laminate 0 shows to be less sensitive.

L2 has, similar like L0, a quad based symmetric layup. They differ by the quad sequence $(-45/45/0/90)$ for L0 and $(-45/0/45/90)$ for L2. Compared to L0 the simulation results show higher values for L2, when the 0° ply near the welding zone is still intact. Once that ply gets separated, the laminate performs worse than L0. This behavior is most likely due to the fact that of all plies in the quasi-isotropic laminate, the 0° plies are delivering the highest proportion to the laminate's bending stiffness. Once they are damaged, the bending stiffness drops dramatically and the flexural deformation is increased, which reduces the load transmission through shear and increases bending and peel stresses.

Figure 3: Virtual testing failure load results over notch overlap u .

The normalized results for the mechanical testing can be seen in Figure 4. The test value highlighted with a circle in Figure 4 serves as the reference for the normalization of the test data. It is related to the simulation value and multiplied by the baseline used for the normalization of the simulation data.

The results of the mechanical testing are indicating a dependence of the resulting failure load to the introduced notch depth machined in the samples. Further L1 is showing significant higher failure load values than L0 and L2.

Figure 4: Mechanical testing failure load results over notch overlap u .

Figure 5 shows the results of the mechanical (MT) and virtual testing (VT). Simulation as well as mechanical testing results show both a tendency of decreasing failure load with increasing notch overlap. The simulation and the tested samples show good agreement for L0 and L2. For L1 the simulation shows an underestimation compared to the failure load of the mechanical tests.

Figure 5: Comparison of virtual and mechanical testing: failure load result over notch overlap u .

6 CONCLUSIONS

The results of the mechanical and virtual testing strongly indicate a dependency of the failure load on the notch depths of the double-notched tension test specimens, which also prove to be layup dependent. This dependency is further influenced by the laminate layup, with a major effect observed when 0° -plies are cut.

For accurate and reliable results, it is crucial to precisely determine the notch depths prior to mechanical testing to ensure all plies are correctly machined.

In scenarios, where intact, continuous plies are still present (configurations with a negative notch overlap parameter u), the test primarily measures the tensile strength of the intact plies rather than the weld performance, leading to questionable conclusions regarding the weld's integrity. Therefore, test configurations with intact continuous plies are not recommended.

While the present study focuses on the influence of the notch overlap parameter u , it is important to acknowledge that the actual position of the overlap can also play a significant role in the resulting failure load, particularly depending on the laminate layup and the position of the 0° -plies. In certain configurations, the notch overlap may be less critical, still delivering usable results for comparison. Further investigations are necessary to comprehensively understand the influence of the notch overlap's position. The notch centroid is proposed as a useful parameter for identifying the actual overlap position, offering the possibility for a more detailed insight, than the current overlap parameter alone.

The double-notched tension test demonstrates potential as a comparative method for evaluating welded laminates, provided that high precision and low tolerance are guaranteed during notch manufacturing. The acceptable tolerance is, however, dependent on the laminate layup and the position of the 0° -plies within. It must be noted that this test method exhibits high sensitivity to relatively small deviations in notch depth, indicating a lack of robustness. Consequently, the applicability of the double-notched tension test requires detailed evaluation for each specific case to ensure its suitability and the reliability of the obtained results.

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